

Societal targeting dimensions in researcher funding: An exploratory approach

Irene Ramos-Vielba^{1*}, Duncan A. Thomas¹, Kaare Aagaard²

¹ Danish Centre for Studies in Research and Research Policy, Department of Political Science, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

² R&D Centre for Quality of Education, Profession Policy and Practice, VIA University College, Aarhus, Denmark

* Corresponding: iravi@ps.au.dk

Abstract

Shaping public research to enhance its societal contribution has become a key policy concern. Against this background, how research funding may stimulate the societal orientation of scientific research – or how funding is societally targeted – has been underexplored. This paper proposes an exploratory approach to characterize societal targeting in individual researcher funding, based on four key societal targeting dimensions: interdisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, prioritized research problems and user-oriented outputs. All these targeting dimensions of funding can potentially shape both researchers' research networks and practices towards societal goals. These dimensions can be identified in context by studying *ex ante* specifications of funding instruments, i.e. rules and conditions for funding provision to researchers. We illustrate the dimensions in various degrees using two real cases of national public research funding. This systematic perspective on funding instrument characteristics then can potentially improve research evaluation, by allowing assessment in more detail of which funding dimensions associate with particular kinds of research ultimately being undertaken.

Keywords

Societal targeting, Dimensions, Research funding, Researchers, Exploratory approach, Funding instruments

1. Introduction

Since the 1990s, a strong belief in the importance of universities as engines of research-driven growth and innovation (Pavitt 2001; Geuna and Muscio 2009; Grimaldi et al. 2011) has led to a growing policy emphasis on how to accelerate and augment the societal contribution of public research. This includes increased articulation of the role of research in tackling grand societal challenges (Boon and Edler 2018; Kuhlmann and Rip 2018) and more explicit ambitions to promote not only economic, but also social, cultural and environmental returns from publicly funded research (Bornmann 2013; Penfield et al. 2014). Relatedly, research funding has transitioned from mainly internal provision via block funding to proportionally more project-based grants, competitively awarded by a wide variety of external organisations, at times with associated societal expectations (Gläser 2019). While there are many drivers behind these changing funding conditions, one of them arguably reflects ambitions by policymakers and funders to increase the 'societal targeting' of research. As a consequence, researchers not only interact with more complicated constellations of funders, but also with

various societally-oriented research funding characteristics (Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018; Aagaard et al. 2021).

These combined developments call for new approaches to the exploration of how research funding seeks to stimulate societal goals of various kinds. Funding is viewed to have a central role in defining the scope, content and direction of public research (Whitley, Gläser and Engwall 2010; Bloch and Sorensen 2015; Aagaard 2017; Young et al. 2017). A better understanding of how research funding more specifically become targeted towards societal objectives, therefore, is vital. This involves an improved understanding of the potential ways in which research funding may shape research towards societal aims, which so far has been a relatively overlooked aspect in existing literature (Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018).

Such an approach is expected to be relevant both in science policy studies and for research evaluation. Research evaluation studies are generally interested in trying to determine and compare how particular research and funding policies, programmes and evaluation arrangements might affect the research that is done in public science (Thomas et al. 2020). More specifically, policymakers, stakeholders and the public are increasingly interested in understanding and assessing societal benefits apparently obtained from research funding (Lepori et al. 2007). Public and private funders also audit and evaluate outcomes from their funding and wish to learn how best to design their funding to be efficient and effective in generating societal and other benefits (Neufeld 2016). However, what is often missing from all these evaluative aims is a detailed characterization and understanding of the funding that was used to achieve research goals, as a prerequisite to understand whether and how funding has actually made a difference to the research that has been undertaken. This link between funding and research is still uncertain (Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018). It is an even more challenging ambition when ideas around what kinds of research funding are actually ‘societal’ have remained nebulous. Attention has been given to the varying design features of funding in general terms, e.g. variations of funding types and objectives. What could enable more bespoke evaluation of societal goals achieved with research funding is to characterize the funding in a standardized way in the first place. Knowing the key societally-relevant dimensions present or absent in funding would then allow more accurate and robust evaluation of what, in comparative terms, researchers have actually used to achieve certain research outcomes. Our paper takes up this challenge by delineating key dimensions of societally targeted researcher funding that are repeatedly present across many kinds of funding that may lead to societal goals, or may have potential to shape research in such directions.

With this article we do not seek to present a full evaluation approach. Rather we develop a vocabulary and a methodological framework to enable us to better characterize such societal targeting features of funding. A better understanding of these factors is a precondition for meaningful subsequent evaluations of how funding eventually shapes research towards societal goals. Our point of departure is the observation that funding may become societally targeted along various *dimensions* and to various *degrees*. Hence, the dominant focus in the literature on fixed categories of funding, labelled exclusively as e.g. mission-oriented or responsive mode, does not allow us to achieve a sufficiently nuanced understanding of such targeting. Instead of looking at broad funding categories or names, we propose to explore selected key targeting dimensions and how they are combined in order to influence the actual conduct of research.

A focus on the researcher level, as opposed to looking at funding systems overall, is particularly important for this type of exploration. Researchers are obligatory points of

passage and thus are vital for our understanding of the way in which funding may shape research (Laudel and Gläser 2014; Rushforth, Franssen and de Rijcke 2019). Individual researchers generate knowledge contributions in a field, determine their research processes, and ultimately decide how they use research funding. How they adapt their behaviour to funding characteristics will ultimately affect both their research practices and their research networks which in turn influence how and to what extent they address societal goals (Williams 2020). It is, therefore, crucial to anchor examination of research funding at this analytical level.

From this researcher-led perspective, we will develop an approach built upon characteristics of funding across various funding contexts. Funding provided to a researcher by any funder may take various forms (e.g. a specific project grant, a particular fellowship or a concrete budget for a time-limited research centre). Across these forms of funding instruments that researchers use we assume that funding may become societally targeted, in various ways, to orient the direction of funded research towards societal goals. Our contention is that a substantial part of this variation can be captured systematically by focusing on selected key targeting dimensions. By focusing on such dimensions of societal targeting in researcher funding, novel analytical possibilities can be developed that account for the increasingly differentiated funding realities that researchers face. Throughout, however, we must also bear in mind that any influence to shape research is likely to be highly mediated, multifaceted and multidirectional.

Based on these premises, this paper presents an exploratory approach to societal targeting of researcher funding. It is structured as follows: First, section 2 reviews literature on changing funding conditions as a core foundation for our work. Next, our approach to societal targeting in research funding is outlined. We first present the selected key societal targeting dimensions of funding instruments (section 3) then illustrate these dimensions in a real context (section 4). Finally, section 5 reflects on the contribution of this approach to research funding studies and concludes with suggestions to take the approach forward in future research.

2. Literature review

This review will first discuss general trends at the level of research policy, highlighting increasing emphasis on funding to support societal goals. Next, the review will show limited knowledge is available about how funders specifically seek to stimulate a societal orientation in research, through the funding they provide to researchers. Finally, we will review emerging research that focuses on the need to understand better how funding instruments work at researcher level, for which we propose an exploratory approach.

2.1 Increasing funding policy emphasis on societal goals

The funding system, and its associated research policy and funding policy trends, has increasingly been recognised as a major factor in the governance of science in the overall public research system (Braun 2003; Edqvist 2003; Sörlin 2007; Whitley, Gläser and Engwall 2010; Bloch and Sorensen 2015; Aagaard 2017; Young et al. 2017; Lepori and Reale 2019). However, funding at this level has been undergoing dramatic changes in recent decades (Lepori and Reale 2019). Most importantly, a critical trend across many countries has been a substantial increase in the share of funding for researchers coming externally from research councils and other funding organisations, whilst the share from block grants is decreasing (Bourke and Butler 1999; Langfeldt 2001; Geuna and Martin 2003; Laudel 2006a; Heinze 2008; Aagaard 2017). Simultaneously, there has been a steady increase in the number of

different project funding instruments available to researchers (Lepori et al. 2007; Franssen and de Rijcke 2019).

There are multiple reasons for these developments. These include New Public Management (NPM) inspired trends, like increased accountability for use of public funding and a strengthened belief in using competition to allocate funding (Nedeva and Boden 2006; Lorenz 2012). Another consideration in the same vein is a renewed focus that supporting excellent research is best done by highly selective funding allocation (Aagaard, Kladakis and Nielsen 2020). However, other parallel developments reflect an apparently growing belief that research should fulfil societal goals, and that funding can provide this stimulation, e.g. by funding research missions (Boon and Edler 2018; Kuhlmann and Rip 2018). Underpinning these trends is the idea that funding can be used to shape research activities, specifically through appropriate *ex ante* funding specifications.

Exploring such funding expectations and specifications that aim to enhance the societal orientation of research is not an easy task. To date, there is little systematic insight from previous research about how this should be done or which aspects of funding and research to focus upon. Similarly, the types of societal contribution that research are expected to deliver, and the mechanisms by which they may be generated, are a moving target, seemingly subject to shifting demands from society, policymakers and research funders (Audretsch 2014). Such changing demands are translated into research funding priorities. An example is how, during the past two decades, both policy and scholarly interests have expanded from largely only considering commercialization and application of research findings, to include broader social, cultural, environmental and economic objectives for funded research. Traditionally, utilitarian research policy concerns (Williams 2020) tended to focus on tangible economic effects of research – such as developing profitable applications, securing intellectual property, and creating marketable products – to the exclusion of considering other potential societal goals of research (Bornmann 2013). Nevertheless, at the policy level, a range of additional funding expectations have also highlighted the possibility of wider uses and benefits of research for society, e.g. for the public sector, in health research, in generating public value, or in tackling grand societal challenges (van der Meulen and Rip 2000; Mostert et al. 2010; Bozeman and Sarewitz 2011). How to trace and compare these various aspects of funding in a systematic way, however, remains largely unaddressed.

2.2 How funders stimulate societal research goals

Even with this increasing funding policy focus on societal goals, and related funder expectations, there is limited knowledge about how the funding instruments that funders provide are actually designed to (attempt to) stimulate societal research goals.

Some steps have been taken in previous research to develop general classifications based on the differing aims and objectives of particular classes of funding. Overall, this group of studies has mainly explored competitive research funding, addressed at a high level of aggregation, using generic categories. Potì and Reale (2007), for instance, consider different kinds of funding: (i) free projects/grants (blind delegation/no restrictions on research topics); (ii) programmes (incentive delegation/funding for defined policy priorities); and (iii) networks (delegation to a network of research organisations/virtual centres). Lepori et al. (2007: 250) distinguish between different project funding types using three similar categories: (i) academic, oriented at scientific results/publications/PhDs; (ii) thematic, oriented at policy priorities; and (iii) innovation, oriented at innovation and economic development in companies. Similarly, Veletanlić and Sá (2020), inspired by Stokes (1997), differentiate between funding aiming to support: (i) pure basic research (Bohr's Quadrant); (ii) pure

applied research (Edison's Quadrant); and (iii) use-inspired basic research (Pasteur's Quadrant). Likewise, the OECD (OECD 2018) and EU have funded studies that worked with similar categorisations – including the 2004–08 PRIME European network and the 2015–17 EU-sponsored Public Funding of Research (PREF) consortium (Jonkers and Zacharewicz 2016).

This literature serves to confirm that there are indeed different funding instruments that can have broadly diverse aims and objectives by design. However, these approaches do not offer much detail about *which* funding characteristics can shape funded research towards societal goals. They also do not highlight particular funding specifications used by funders, and do not map which funder expectations systematically underpin the various types of funding employed by funders. Some previous funding studies have examined the specific aims of certain funding types. However, these have typically been programmes with narrow, non-societal aims, e.g. to stimulate breakthrough research (Heinze 2008; Prendergast, Brown and Britton 2008). Studies of which funding characteristics are associated with societally oriented research objectives remain missing (Logar 2011; Biegelbauer, Palfinger and Mayer 2020).

Without such knowledge from previous research, we need to begin from first principles. First, it must be assumed that funders may enact their priorities and expectations through potentially multiple different levers, in terms of the funding instrument specifications they develop. Second, it should be assumed that some of these levers may be more or less amenable to the research they fund being able to fulfil specific policy objectives. Third, there is a need to identify and understand which funding characteristics can attempt to steer research towards societal outcomes. Relying on generic funding types and the names of funding instruments will not provide this understanding. Focusing on identifying relevant characteristics and specifications instead seems a useful way, based on the limits and gaps of previous research, to improve understanding of how funding may shape research towards societal goals.

2.3 A diversified societal targeting funding reality at researcher level

Consequently, there also seems to be insufficient attention given in previous research to how funding actually manifests at researcher level. This is crucial to consider. Transformation of funding landscapes into increasingly multi-actor, multi-level systems, has led to variegated funding actors operating concurrently (e.g. supranational, national, regional, public, private, philanthropic). These varied funders can have many different objectives (Sörlin 2007; Boon and Edler 2018; Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018; Kuhlmann and Rip 2018; Wagner 2019; Aagaard et al. 2021). The increase in numbers and varieties of funders is acknowledged in literature, but its implications have seemingly been overlooked. Some recent studies have called for a reality check of this new funding situation (Lepori 2011; Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018; OECD 2018; Gläser 2019; Cocos and Lepori 2020; Aagaard et al. 2021). However, both the inherent diversification of actors potentially attempting to use funding to achieve different goals, and the resulting complexity of funding environments, challenge previous approaches to study research funding. Certain funders are increasingly important in some settings, like charities and supranational funding agencies (Nedeva 2013; Luukkonen 2014). Entirely new schemes have emerged in others (Lepori et al. 2007). The overall research funding environment is now diverse, with more variety of funding for researchers.

This review of funding trends underpins our approach to researcher funding. The progressive incorporation of policymakers' designs to enhance societal relevance of research has resulted in increased societal orientation of funding policy. More heterogeneous funding

provided by funders has also broadened possibilities for how funded research might contribute to societal goals. Both trends permeate the funding reality researchers then navigate in acquiring and using funding instruments. This situation generates a need to identify funding characteristics potentially associated with policy and funder expectations to shape research towards societal goals. This context still leaves a broad interpretation of how a societal orientation is embodied in funding instruments that researchers use. At policy level, the term societal may reflect concern for global or grand challenges or some expression of national interests and needs. From a funding provision perspective, this may also involve consideration of the demands and concerns of more local groups of stakeholders. It is important to note that all such notions may then eventually manifest in the societal characteristics of researchers' funding instruments.

3. Societal targeting in researcher funding instruments

The exploratory approach we propose addresses the above shortcomings in previous literature. It enables both characterization and further observation of societal targeting in researcher funding contexts. The characterization examines funding instruments through the lens of their *ex ante* specifications, focused on a set of dimensions we consider key indicators of societal targeting.

3.1 *Ex ante* specifications

To begin our approach, we consider that signals of increased attention towards societal goals of research by policymakers and funders have been translated into identifiable funding instrument characteristics. Funder expectations related to societal goals for funded research may be expressed as tangible, objective funding instrument features. To investigate this systematically, we foreground selected instrument specifications. This assumes that funding policy discourse (Skupien and Ruffin 2020) is translated into funding characteristics specified by funders. Paying regard to these *ex ante* specifications is a precondition for researchers to obtain this funding (Torka 2018). We will label these characteristics as key societal targeting dimensions of funding instruments.

The funding instrument is taken to standardize a unit of analysis in our approach, expressing funder expectations related to societal goals for research. In this way, a funding instrument becomes universal across all types of funding. Even when a funder has programmes for research funding with certain specificities, these will ultimately be executed as discrete instruments (e.g. project grants, fellowships or other) allocated to researchers. In this sense, internal funding can also be considered a funding instrument, e.g. when a university provides competitive funding, under certain conditions, to a researcher from the institution's block funding. Internal funding can also have specifications, for instance, to create societally-themed, internal, cross-faculty research centres in a university, or there can be small internal research projects on societal issues (Luukkonen and Thomas 2016).

Funding instruments vary in how they detail expectations and orientations. This has been captured for the example of multiple funding instruments that all aim to stimulate breakthrough research, but do so using differing funding specifications (Heinze 2008). Similarly, numerous funding instruments attempt to provide researchers freedom to undertake risky research but use varying descriptions of requirements. They can specify the funded research must be at the frontier (e.g. European Research Council grants) (Nedeva 2013; Luukkonen 2014) or provide money without stating expectations, as with unconditioned research prize money (Franssen et al. 2018). Similarly, we do not consider societal targeting to be a binary, all-or-nothing characteristic of funding instruments. We instead highlight key

societal targeting dimensions aiming to increase the likelihood of the funded research contributing to address societal goals, but likely with differences in how these dimensions are understood in specific contexts, and in different research fields. To account for such variety, this paper provides a systematic and standardized approach to characterize the societal targeting in research funding.

3.2 Four key dimensions

We address funding instruments only from an *ex ante* perspective. This means looking at conditions and rules of funding instruments to discern key societal targeting dimensions. To enable this to be a standard approach for analysis, these dimensions need to be explicit, objective, factual and observable in funding documentation (e.g. in funding calls, funding guidelines, funding contracts). We consider them a collective, given each dimension may shape research networks and practices, i.e. shaping may occur because one or more of the dimensions is present.

Based on observing trends of policy discourse, investigating funder practices and relevant insights in existing literature (e.g. Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018; Aagaard et al. 2021), we consider two overall aspects of research enable us to capture key targeting markers that can indicate funding of research towards societal aims. The first of these is research network compositions. With this we are interested in explicit indications of which knowledge co-producers – either from academia or from other sectors – have been included in the funded research. The second marker is the research practices that are being funded. This refers to funding specifications related to topic orientations and/or certain types of research outputs. These markers cannot always be assumed to be associated with direct funding expressions of definite funding policy rationales. They may also not necessarily be obvious simply from the name of a funding instrument. Nevertheless, these two analytical markers allow us to capture relevant likely indications of societal targeting that may shape funded research to facilitate or enhance its societal potential.

Moving into more detail regarding research networks, we can differentiate between societal targeting of interdisciplinarity networks and of transdisciplinarity networks. Both forms of societal targeting seemingly aim to increase the degree and/or affect the type of research collaboration and participation that is being funded. This funding may influence the presence of academics from different disciplines (interdisciplinarity) and/or the involvement of non-academic stakeholders in society (transdisciplinarity), e.g. private companies or non-profit organisations being included into the knowledge co-production network of the funded researchers. The apparent logic underpinning both types is that interpersonal research networks, in some way, can be beneficial for funded research to reach societal goals. Previous research has shown these network forms can lead to knowledge cross-fertilization and further research capacity building among the participating actors (Huang 2014). Involvement of academic and/or non-academics in funded research can, however, vary in practice. Some actors will participate in only a nominal way; others may be integrally involved in making research-related decisions, creating knowledge and publishing together (i.e. in co-decision, co-creation, or co-publication activities).

Funding specifications concerning research practice dimensions can be considered regarding two key aspects, societal targeting in terms of: pursuit of specified societally-oriented research problems; and specification for research outputs to be in some way user-oriented (e.g. policy reports, policy briefings, outreach materials, open datasets, and commercialisation related outputs like patents, marketable products or services). Below we provide further detail about each of these four key dimensions.

3.2.1 Interdisciplinarity

The societal aims of funded research may benefit from particular knowledge production collaboration features. For our first dimension, funding instrument specifications may state or imply that theories or methods need to be integrated from more than one discipline in the funded research. A primary underlying reason to foster interdisciplinarity would be that the funded research issue may not be satisfactorily tackled if just one discipline in isolation is mobilized, particularly in the case of multifaceted societal problems such as climate change or resource security (Rylance 2015; Bromham, Dinnage and Hua 2016). Instead, this requires some combination of specialised contribution from diverse disciplines. Thus, integration of multiple areas of research insights and approaches could be considered a desirable feature of the funded scientific knowledge creation process, and research funding may play an important role in fostering such an interdisciplinary programme (Lyll et al. 2013). In this sense, interdisciplinary research is considered a synthesis of expertise increasingly present in grant proposals (Laudel 2006b).

Likewise, further applications of funded research (e.g. towards technology development or public policy improvement) could be seen as needing insights from across different disciplines to best facilitate implementation. A requirement for interdisciplinarity may be explicitly included in funding specifications. Interdisciplinarity, as a key societal targeting dimension of funding instruments then relies on an apparent rationale that the funded knowledge contribution to society – particularly, its value and significance for real-world contexts – is likely to be enriched by use of diverse cognitive perspectives and by spanning epistemic boundaries in both science and practice. The expected research undertaken via the funding instrument would be inherently of a collaborative nature from a disciplinary point of view.

In some contexts, knowledge exchanges between different disciplines can be present as a research characteristic not necessarily related to societal orientation. In other contexts, interdisciplinarity can however be indicative of societal targeting of funding, because integrating across disciplinary perspectives has been associated with societal orientation of research (Huzair et al. 2013; Lyll et al. 2013; Bammer 2017). Additionally, whether interdisciplinarity alone may have some societal aim is not the only consideration. Our key dimensions are a collective characterization overall of a funding instrument. It is therefore important to consider how interdisciplinarity appears in combination with varying levels of the other three dimensions. Therefore, although not all interdisciplinary modes of research may be fundamentally aimed at societal purposes, this dimension may yet contribute to expand or reinforce collaborative interdisciplinary scholar networks beyond their previously existing levels (e.g. in terms of composition, role, involvement). Empirical investigation might then reveal whether the funding specifications have shaped how researchers address interdisciplinary collaboration.

3.2.2 Transdisciplinarity

Similarly, our second societal targeting dimension relates to funding instrument specifications for inclusion of non-academics into the knowledge production process. The basis for this argument is that increasing complexity of real-world problems requires incorporating epistemologies and methodologies – from policy, private and social sectors (Lyll et al. 2013) – that go beyond simply academic disciplinary research (Walter et al. 2007). This is a specific understanding of transdisciplinarity, dating back to the 1980s in Europe, putting distinctive emphasis on participation of a wider range of society stakeholders (Klein 2006, 2008). Such

inclusive processes can integrate cultural values, practical knowledge and know-how from different types of practitioners (Hansson and Polk 2018). The involvement of non-scientific domains is therefore assumed to facilitate socially robust knowledge (Polk 2014). Additionally, broader insights, tacit knowledge and grassroots skills may also contribute to the generation of more effective responses to societal problems and final societal benefits. Knowledge co-creation with stakeholders in society then follows a logic of expanding the perspective of approaches throughout the research process to enhance research results.

Funding of this kind exists, for example, in strategic funding requiring academic researchers to collaborate with non-academics (Feldman and Graddy-Reed 2014). Like the other key dimensions, transdisciplinarity will be of different degrees, somewhere on a spectrum. For instance, some indications of this dimension in funding instruments may include *ex ante* specifications on publicly sharing of research data and, in some occasions, the funded researcher foregoing intellectual property rights or licensing revenues. Another variation on this dimension can be seen in a growing number of programmes at national and supranational levels, like the European Union, calling explicitly for wider dissemination and improved utilization of findings by involving firms and other non-academic actors in the research process (Perkmann et al. 2021). Additional transdisciplinarity requirements could include funding of formal or informal tasks by stakeholders, e.g. to provide advice, to add legitimacy to a piece of research, or to contribute insights regarding technical and instrumental solutions based on contextual non-academic knowledge.

Overall, the rationales for such transdisciplinarity specifications are to redraw traditional boundaries between research, stakeholders, and citizens. This is in line with post-normal science (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1993) and rethinking the societal role of research. Still in this vein, integrating more collective perspectives from local knowledge and non-researcher expertise promotes democratization of public research, when the funded research is expected to be highly inclusive in participative terms.

3.2.3 Prioritized research problems

A third key dimension involves looking for specifications of the particular research problems to be addressed within the topic orientation of the funded research. This targeting will then affect the research content, such as its research questions and ultimate goals. It may also have implications for the research approach, methods used, and experimental scope. Research funding, therefore, becomes an important driver in identifying research problems that need to be tackled effectively (Lyall et al. 2013). The rationale for this targeting dimension is that problem-solving research is societally desirable, and that explicitly indicating it in funding specifications may cause it to happen, rather than leaving these matters entirely unspecified.

This third societal targeting dimension may then influence both research processes and outputs, aiming to generate knowledge that is sensitive to concrete societal needs, and is relevant for certain societal actors (e.g. for an industrial sector, for types of patients). Previous research has highlighted some instruments that seek to increase the orientation of funded research towards pre-defined priority areas (Geuna 2001; Braun 2003; Lepori et al. 2007). Researchers are also known to adjust their research towards the direction of societally targeted funding instruments, in various ways, e.g. in the case of provision of public funding instruments for stem cell research (Kishi 2020). If this dimension can be discerned in funding specifications, the knowledge generated by the funded research, therefore, can likely be expected to be suitably applicable in relation to the identified problem-solving needs.

3.2.4 User-oriented outputs

The fourth key dimension looks for funding specifications on the funded research outputs to have user-orientation. Like in the three other key dimensions, this indicates a particular interest that the research being funded should contribute valuable knowledge to society. For this dimension, the generation of outputs in adaptable forms for different end-users is specifically considered (e.g. for local communities, large businesses, national policymakers, broader audiences). This dimension targets that funding then leads to research outputs that can be transferred to diverse research beneficiaries for them to appropriate into practice. How research outputs are oriented to users, and used by specific users, then becomes relevant for science as a societal public good (Yin et al. 2021).

Knowledge production to fit potential users may, for instance, be stimulated through openness throughout research activities (Olmos-Peñuela, Benneworth and Castro-Martínez 2018). Funded researchers may also widen their channels of dissemination to try to produce more transferable, actionable research outputs to end-users. For example, this might include tailoring research findings for different target audiences, translating findings into more accessible/easily understandable terms or into multiple languages, and producing outputs in varied formats, i.e. not only academic papers but also knowledge translation products that are easily assimilated by different audiences (Grimshaw et al. 2012). The underlying rationale for this dimension then is that the funded research would be expected to be easy to absorb for users and/or be widely usable in societal settings, public policy contexts or in the private sector.

Table 1 provides an overview of these four key societal targeting dimensions of research funding, the aspects of research activity they target, the knowledge contributions to society being implicitly or explicitly targeted, the markers of these targeting in research, and the nature of the expected research that would arise from the funding.

Table 1. Four key societal targeting dimensions in research funding instruments

	Societal targeting dimensions	Targeted aspects	Targeted knowledge contributions to society	Targeting markers	Expected research
I	<i>Interdisciplinarity</i>	Research process	Cognitive perspectives Epistemic complementarity	Research networks (e.g. composition, role, involvement)	Inherently collaborative
T	<i>Transdisciplinarity</i>		Non-academic / tacit knowledge Co-creation of knowledge		Inclusively participative
P	<i>Prioritized research problems</i>		Problem-solving / societal needs Sensitive & relevant knowledge	Research practices (e.g. priorities, approaches, methods)	Suitably applicable
O	<i>User-oriented outputs</i>	Research output Practical & useful knowledge Benefit & value to society	Widely usable		

In practice, any number of the four key dimensions could be seen in an actual funding instrument. For example, an instrument with all four dimensions would be societally targeted to address societal goals through extensive collaboration across academic disciplines, with broad participation of non-academic actors, to tackle a concrete prioritized research problem so as to ensure adequate applicability of the funded research, and would be expected to make funded research outputs usable in diverse contexts.

4. Societal targeting dimensions in context

We now look at these societal targeting dimensions of funding in context. This demonstrates how the four societal targeting dimensions can be observed, for real cases, based on funders'

ex ante specifications for instruments a researcher may use. We present two examples. This serves to illustrate there can be nuances in apparent degree of societal targeting, i.e. in how explicitly a funder expresses targeting. We suggest this variance of degree is also important to consider. It may result in differing influence across the dimensions for how a funded researcher conducts their research and composes their research networks and practices. Thus, research might be shaped in response to the totality of how the four dimensions are present in a funding instrument.

Our two examples are both current, ongoing national programmes for research funding. They are selected from systematic reviews of funding policy and programme characteristics by the OECD. The first example is one that OECD considers a high level mission-oriented funding policy in Denmark.¹ This is Grand Solutions, from the public national research funder, Innovation Fund Denmark² (IFD). IFD has a legal mandate, via state executive order, for its funding to support development and application of knowledge and technology to strengthen research and innovation, and to achieve growth and employment in Denmark.³ IFD describes GS as funding for ‘ambitious, cross-cutting research and innovation projects that can create new, concrete solutions to important societal challenges, and which create value for Denmark’.⁴ The second example the OECD considers traceable back to high-level policy by the Norwegian Ministry of Agriculture and Food, to allocate resources to its unified national public funder, the Research Council of Norway (RCN). This is with explicit expectation that funding programmes will be developed to support research in a specific sector, in this case, bio-economy. This programme is BIONÆR, RCN funding aiming to contribute ‘greatly to strengthening and developing knowledge and skills for bio-based industries’ by funding research to be undertaken within ‘an extensive co-operation ecosystem across institutions, sectors and countries’ (Antón 2020: 139).

Table 2 isolates *ex ante* specifications from funding documentation for Denmark’s GS and Norway’s BIONÆR. This is based on public website wordings, text in work programmes and in other relevant documents, including guidelines for applications and their assessment. From these wordings we attempt to analyse their content to determine the presence of the four key societal targeting dimensions and the degree of targeting for each dimension. We follow a somewhat analogous logic to how the level of delegation from a funder to a researcher has been considered in previous studies (Braun 2003; Poti and Reale 2007). A degree can exist where the funder retains authority over what research will be funded, in terms of the dimension expressed. Incorporating this targeted dimension into the funded research is, therefore, targeted to a ‘compulsory’ degree, as we show in the table for aspects of BIONÆR. There can also be a case where the funder essentially delegates authority to the researcher to determine whether and how to incorporate one of the dimensions from the framework. This the funder can do by explicitly stating a particular research aspect is not required or by not mentioning it at all. This other end of the degree scale we would label as a targeting dimension being ‘not required’ by the funder. A third possible degree can exist in funding instrument specifications when a funder explicitly mentions a dimension but does not specify it as mandatory to include in the funded research. It is partially delegated from the funder to the researcher. It is still mentioned and highlighted, but is not compulsory. This middle degree may be phrased as an aspect being advantageous to address, or will be given particular emphasis when a research proposal is assessed potentially to be funded by the programme. We see this ‘encouraged’ degree for several GS dimensions.

¹ Available at: <https://stip.oecd.org/stip/moip/case-studies/22>

² Available at: <https://innovationsfonden.dk/en/about-innovation-fund-denmark>

³ Available at: <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2017/1150>

⁴ Available at: <https://innovationsfonden.dk/en/programmes/grand-solutions>

Table 2. Societal targeting dimensions observed for two illustrative examples

	Innovation Fund Denmark - Grand Solutions		Research Council of Norway - BIONÆR	
	<i>Ex ante specifications</i>	Degree	<i>Ex ante specifications</i>	Degree
Interdisciplinarity	<p>“...collaborative projects with no mandatory composition of the consortia (i.e. no requirement of having ... academic partners ... in the projects)”</p> <p>“In the assessment ... particular emphasis is placed on ... expected value creation through innovation in other fields”</p>	<p>No mandatory requirement for academic partners</p> <p>‘Particular emphasis’ on value created in other (research) fields</p> <p>→ Encouraged</p>	<p>“...must be based on integrated, interdisciplinary knowledge-building”</p> <p>“The inherent need for coherence and interdisciplinarity in knowledge-building for the bioeconomy places new demands on research groups; these must work together more than ever to produce genuinely interdisciplinary and socially relevant knowledge”</p> <p>“The BIONAER programme will promote the development of high-quality research groups working within the social sciences as well as collaboratively with research groups in, for example, biology and technology disciplines”</p>	<p>Research ‘must be based’ on ‘interdisciplinary knowledge-building’</p> <p>Research groups ‘must work together’ in a ‘genuinely interdisciplinary’ way</p> <p>Specific disciplines are funded to work together</p> <p>→ Compulsory</p>
Transdisciplinarity	<p>“...covers the complete value chain and is defined as collaborative projects with no mandatory composition of the consortia (i.e. no requirement of having industrial... partners...or SMEs in the projects)”</p> <p>“It is ... advantageous if beneficiaries of the project outcomes and other key stakeholders are active participants in the design and development of the project”</p>	<p>No mandatory requirement for industrial partners and SMEs</p> <p>‘Advantageous’ transdisciplinary practice (beneficiaries and stakeholders as ‘active participants’)</p> <p>→ Encouraged</p>	<p>“Research activities funded ... must contribute to solving specific industry challenges ... enhancing value creation by further developing existing industries and facilitating the establishment of new industrial activities in Norway”</p> <p>“The programme will employ a set of instruments designed to meet industry’s knowledge needs”</p>	<p>No mandatory requirement for industry partners</p> <p>Research needs to ‘meet industry’s knowledge needs’</p> <p>→ Encouraged</p>
Prioritized research problem	<p>“...ambitious, cross-cutting research and innovation projects that can create new, concrete solutions to important societal challenges, and which create value for Denmark”</p> <p>“The application must clearly display and define the value creation, as well as show how it is measured and guaranteed”</p> <p>“... assessed based on ... whether the applied knowledge and developed technology and innovation leads to growth and employment in Denmark and/or contributes to solving tangible societal challenges”</p>	<p>Concrete solutions, value creation (incl. applied knowledge) mentioned</p> <p>‘Societal challenges’ indicated, not precisely prescribed or prioritised</p> <p>→ Encouraged</p>	<p>“The BIONAER programme was launched against the ... strategic backdrop ... [of] [t]he major global societal challenges (grand challenges)”</p> <p>“Research activities funded ... must contribute to solving specific industry challenges”</p> <p>“The programme will incorporate cross-cutting perspectives such as closed-loop systems, sustainability and value creation into all its activities”</p> <p>“Projects will have to address topics within the overall thematic area of the BIONAER programme; normally there will be no other thematic limitations”</p>	<p>Strategic backdrop: ‘grand challenges’</p> <p>Overall thematic priority but ‘no other limitations’</p> <p>Particular research methods suggested (‘closed-loop systems’)</p> <p>→ Encouraged</p>

User-oriented outputs	<p><i>“The project must create societal value and/or economic value in public and private companies in Denmark and/or for beneficiaries in the Danish society, e.g. citizens, the state, regions and municipalities.</i></p> <p><i>“Please describe any resources needed and any expected barriers for the societal adoption of the project results”</i></p> <p><i>“In the assessment ... particular emphasis is placed on ... descriptions of actions undertaken to ensure that the beneficiaries implement the results or take the results to the next step”</i></p>	<p>Expectation of actions to further societal adoption of results</p> <p>‘Particular emphasis’ on creation of societal value for sectors, direct / indirect beneficiaries / end-users</p> <p>→ Encouraged</p>	<p><i>“The programme will employ dialogue-based, flexible work forms with a conscious focus on communication as a means of ensuring that it meets the needs of the research community and society at large”</i></p> <p><i>“ ... requires focus on market orientation, innovation and efficiency”</i></p> <p><i>“Activities under the BIONAER programme must consciously place all production in a wider market context. Contact with consumers and an understanding of consumer desires and needs will be vital here”</i></p> <p><i>“Evaluation of results, impacts and societal outcomes from the programme must seek to document the benefit ... for industry, the public authorities, competence development and society at large”</i></p>	<p>‘Conscious focus’ on ‘needs’ of ‘society at large’, ‘market orientation’; ‘understanding’ consumers is ‘vital’</p> <p>‘Must’ document benefit of ‘results, impacts and societal outcomes’ for various users or stakeholders</p> <p>→ Compulsory</p>
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Sources: Grand Solutions and BIONÆR – websites, funding descriptions, work programmes and application guidelines.

It is interesting to note how funders express societal targeting degree in these instrument specifications. Certain words – ‘vital’, ‘must’, ‘consciously’, ‘genuinely’ – seem to indicate a ‘compulsory’ targeting degree, presumably where the funder is careful not to overly restrict researcher autonomy. For ‘encouraged’, we see funders using words like ‘advantageous’, ‘emphasis’, ‘contribute’ and ‘expected’. This probably affords greater discretion to a researcher in how these dimensions are addressed. We also see wording indicating ‘not required’ for a particular aspect, or ‘no mandatory’ characteristics. However, all these wordings can be modified or nuanced by other statements elsewhere in the specifications, and the four dimensions should be considered collectively.

We also see a spectrum of implied societal goals across these instruments – mirroring our earlier indication that funding policy and provision layers can lead to this notion being treated in different contexts. In GS, we see societal expectations framed as ‘value, employment and growth for Denmark’ (i.e. national concerns). In BIONÆR we see mixed concerns for ‘new industrial activities in Norway’ (i.e. national and sector specific concerns) alongside mention of major global societal challenges.

The societal targeting dimensions and degrees characterisations shown in Table 2 may eventually relate to differing potentials to shape the research a researcher will undertake using the funding instruments. A researcher with a GS funding instrument is being ‘encouraged’ to address all four key societal targeting dimensions in their research. How far they exert themselves to (re-)shape their research to do this would need to be studied. It may however be shaped by an understanding that these are not ‘compulsory’ to consider. For BIONÆR, two dimensions are indeed specified as ‘compulsory’. For interdisciplinarity, this even includes discipline-to-discipline examples, suggesting acceptable scopes of interdisciplinarity. For user-oriented outputs, explicit ‘compulsory’ indications are given that the researcher will be evaluated to determine whether they actually achieved user orientation with their results, impacts and societal outcomes. This targeting degree may then be a stronger shaping

influence upon the research of researchers funded by this instrument, compared to the GS case.

5. Discussion and conclusions

Comparing researchers according to the societal targeting of their funding

This dimensions-based approach contributes and makes it possible to move from a variable and nebulous understanding of societal funding to four key dimensions that we can look for in funding instruments that researchers use, and which we can see may have various nuanced degrees suggestive of their potential to shape a researcher's research. Contrasted with, for instance, studying funding instruments based on their names or broad categories (e.g. labelled as 'mission-oriented' or 'grand challenges' funding), it is now possible to determine a standardized basis, by which the relative shaping potential of the funding these researchers have, can be compared. By reifying the societal aspect of the funding into the presence or absence, and apparent degree of each of the four societal targeting dimensions – then considering their aggregate potential as a collective set – we now have a way to compare the societal shaping potential of differing researcher funding situations.

We can further suggest that it is not only which societal targeting dimensions are present in a researcher's funding instrument that matters – i.e. whether this is one, two or more of the dimensions simultaneously. The degree of each dimension is also likely important in potentially influencing what research will be done with the funding. In practice, this kind of shaping would need to be studied empirically on a case-by-case basis. The targeting degrees – alone or mixed across (potentially) all four in an instrument – may not correlate directly with shaping towards those societal research characteristics in every context. However, this four dimensions approach nevertheless provides a standardized, systematic set of focus areas to look for potential shaping in: (i) the presence or absence of a particular societal targeting dimension; (ii) how societal targeting dimensions interact when more than one is present in a funding instrument; and (iii) what influence on shaping of research networks and practices results from differing degrees of specification of each of the societal targeting dimensions.

For such a determination, key characteristics of the researcher's networks and practices might be studied before and after a researcher uses a particular funding instrument. This could include, e.g. for interdisciplinarity, how interdisciplinary the researcher's research was before the instrument was acquired, what kinds of academics from which disciplines they collaborated with beforehand and how this changed (or not) because of the funding instrument. For transdisciplinarity, the same assessment would be needed of the kinds and roles of non-academic partners present in the researcher's research before and after. Similarly, before/after views could be obtained for how research problems were prioritised, and for how orientation of their research outputs was determined.

A primary benefit of a standardized analysis is that it makes possible a more systematic and comparable understanding across contexts. Being able to compare the societal targeting of researcher funding in this way, as a proxy for shaping potential of the funding, may produce valuable insights for policymakers, research funders, research evaluators and scholars. It allows more nuanced, systematic understanding of the role of funding designs and orientations – the societal targeting dimensions and degrees – associated with various societal contributions of public science. This could lead to advances in design, provision and monitoring of funding, informed by an appropriate framing of researchers' real-world funding contexts, and the degrees and dimensions of societal targeting presented to them by their funding resources. Similarly, evaluation of research results may inform research management

and research policy. Performance-based assessment of researchers often considers how they have used prior funding to decide upon future funding allocation (Geuna and Martin 2003). Within such assessments, impact evaluation also assesses how researchers have performed in terms of the scientific and societal value of their research (Smit and Hessels 2021). Understanding the societal targeting of the funding researchers received would then provide a better baseline for such evaluations. This would make it possible to evaluate what a researcher has achieved, more accurately based upon what kind of funding they used to perform their research. The key dimensions perspective we have outlined in this paper could then help such evaluations, by accommodating differences in the potential societal shaping of different kinds of societally targeted research funding in researcher performance.

Analytical challenges for further research

An analytical challenge we should mention as a subject for separate further research is that researchers are known potentially to hold not one but multiple funding instruments at once. In such researcher funding situations, there are known to be various kinds of potential interactions between concurrent funding instruments (Shapira and Wang 2010; Hellström and Jacob 2017; Gläser and Serrano Velarde 2018; OECD 2018; Aagaard et al. 2021). One such example of interaction, for instance, is when a researcher co-uses some or all of their concurrent funding instruments to pursue connected lines of research, where they are compatible to do so. Co-funding of this kind has, for example, been observed in research fields such as global nanotechnology (Wang and Shapira 2011), and in renewable energy research and food science (Aagaard et al. 2021).

This could of course also happen in terms of interactions between the societal targeting dimensions and degrees of one funding instrument a researcher uses, and those of other instruments they concurrently hold. Such interactions could occur in simple ways, along the analytical components addressed by the four key societal targeting dimensions. This could include, e.g. if concurrent funding instruments involve the same academic actors (interdisciplinary collaboration), non-academic stakeholders (transdisciplinarity participation), overlapping prioritized research problems, users or outputs for users. Interactions of this kind, occurring within the instrument mix or funding configuration of instruments a researcher holds (Thomas, Ramos-Vielba and Aagaard 2020; Aagaard et al. 2021), could also relate to whether the instruments originate from the same funder or from separate funders, and thus likely have different dimensions societally targeted, and perhaps a wide range of differing degrees.

Finally, this would move from characterization of the funding that a researcher uses to comparing the broad idea of societal funding across researchers in a standardized way. This has been the primary focus on the key dimensions societal targeting framework we have outlined in this paper. It would have to incorporate consideration of varying agency that researchers enact in how they acquire funding and respond to characteristics of funding (Laudel 2006a). This kind of study would allow exploration of how each researcher responds to particular societal targeting dimensions and degrees. This would also be the case for certain mixes of configurations of these in instances where researchers are mobilising several societally targeted funding instruments simultaneously. In connection with this, certain characteristics of the funded principal investigator, such as previous experience with socially relevant research, could be considered a possibly influential or moderating factor in a specific empirical investigation. Additionally, other pressures for social relevance, such as how progress is monitored by funders, could be also further explored in connection with shaping of funded research towards societal goals. Overall, these further research areas could help to expand our exploratory approach to societal targeting key dimensions and degrees in

researcher funding instruments, to incorporate additional dynamics that may be found in the kinds of complicated, multi-funding researcher situations that can now be seen across parts of contemporary science.

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